

FAILURE MECHANISMS IN CENOSPHERE EPOXY SYNTACTIC FOAMS UNDER UNIAXIAL COMPRESSION

Ruoxuan Huang¹, Peifeng Li¹, and Tong Liu²

¹School of Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering, Nanyang Technological University
50 Nanyang Avenue, Singapore 639798

Email: huan0237@e.ntu.edu.sg, peifeng.li@ntu.edu.sg, web page: <http://www.ntu.edu.sg>

²Singapore Institute of Manufacturing Technology
71 Nanyang Drive, Singapore 638075

Email: tliu@simtech.a-star.edu.sg, web page: <http://www.simtech.a-star.edu.sg>

Keywords: Cenosphere, Failure, Syntactic foam, X-ray microtomography

ABSTRACT

Syntactic foams made of cenospheres and epoxy matrix have become attractive in marine, automotive and aerospace applications due to their light weight and good specific strength. The use of the foam in the structural components requires the understanding of the mechanical behaviour under various loading conditions. This work investigated the behaviour and the associated failure mechanisms in cenosphere epoxy syntactic foams subjected to uniaxial compression. In situ x-ray micro-tomography (XMT) was performed to observe the external and internal morphological changes in the foam. At the early stage of deformation, the compressive damage caused by hydrostatic stresses was observed in the central part of the foam specimen. As the deformation increased, the barrelling effect in the cylindrical specimen raised the shear stress along the specimen diagonal. Then, the hydrostatic stress fully crushed the central part and resulted in the densification. Finally the shear stress induced the macro-cracks in the epoxy matrix along the diagonal direction, and the longitudinal cracks also occurred on the surface of the specimen due to the lateral expansion. It was also observed that the cenospheres deformed and fractured in various parts of the specimen during the compression. The XMT observations of individual cenospheres revealed that the cracks occurred in the cenospheres along the compression direction and caused the separation into fragments. The failure mode of the cenospheres can be summarised as the vertical splitting.

1 INTRODUCTION

A cenosphere with geometry of large diameter to wall thickness ratio is a kind of ceramic hollow sphere mainly made of alumina and silica and filled with air or other gases [1]. As a byproduct of coal combustion, the low cost and particle density make it an ideal choice for developing lightweight composites when cenospheres are filled into a matrix of polymer (syntactic foams) [2]. Meanwhile the inclusion of cenospheres may provide enhanced mechanical properties like elastic modulus, toughness, energy absorption and increased isotropic compression.

In the past two decades, the investigations on the cenosphere filled polymer syntactic foams (CPSF) focused on their mechanical properties, such as compression, tension, fracture, impact resistance, flexural response, damping and creep [3-5]. However, there have been much fewer studies on the deformation history and associated failure mechanisms of the material; almost no study discussed about the failure in microscopic scale, such as the failure process of an individual cenosphere, micro cracks or localized fracture of matrix. To determine the lifetime of the industrial products made of CPSF, it is vital to understand the failure mechanisms of the material in different length scales. Researchers usually use the post-test characterization of the fracture surface to investigate the failure mechanisms [6, 7], then analyze the change in microstructure. Though the post-test method was effective and easy to be performed, the unloading and cooling effects, such as elastic recovery, shrinkage or crack closure cannot be avoided. Therefore the post-test investigation may not be credible for the observation of materials deformation. To overcome the issue, attention has been

paid on the in situ experiments which can provide global information on the material during the whole experiments, thus the microstructural evolution can be followed [8].

With the increase of complexity in structures of functional materials, investigations of the damage evolution and the failure mechanism of a material become the complicated 3D problems. Hence 3D characterization of microstructure is essential. X-ray micro-tomography (XMT) allows for the 3D observation of internal microstructural features in materials with very high resolution, and recently it has been proved to be a powerful non-destructive tool in characterizing the composite materials [9], especially for porous materials [10]. Hence if a foam material can be tested in situ coupled with the XMT imaging, a better understanding of the internal morphology, as well as the morphological changes as a result of the test can be derived. It is believed the in situ tests with XMT inspection will offer a new insight in scientific research.

The aim of this work is to investigate the quasi-static compression behaviors and the damage evolution of CPSF. The uniaxial compression behavior of the material was first analyzed. The examinations of the XMT slices obtained by in situ compression tests with XMT inspections were used to summarize the damage history and the associated failure mechanisms of the CPSF specimen as well as the individual cenospheres.

2 EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

2.1 Fabrication of the CPSF specimen

The CPSF in this study was fabricated by mechanically mixing the cenospheres and epoxy resin pastes. CENOSTAR ES500 cenospheres and Epicote 1006A epoxy resin were used as the fillers and matrix respectively. The volume fraction of fillers was 45%. The preparation process involved the following steps: first the cenospheres were added into the epoxy resin while stirred carefully until the material became the uniform slurry; then the slurry was left in a vacuum oven for 10 minutes to reduce the gas bubbles introduced by the stirring; the mixture was subsequently molded in an aluminum mold coated with release agent and cured at room temperature for 24 hours; finally the CPSF specimen were taken out of the mold and cut into the cylindrical specimens.

2.2 Mechanical tests

Quasi-static compression tests were conducted on an INSTRON 5569 universal mechanical testing machine fitted with a 50 kN load cell at room temperature. Cylindrical specimens with an aspect ratio 1:1 and diameter 10mm were used in the compression tests. The deformation history of the specimens was recorded in a JAI BM-500 high resolution camera. To minimize the interfacial friction during compression, all the specimens were lubricated with the Castrol LMX grease.

2.3 In-situ compression tests with XMT inspections

XMT scans were performed to get an insight into the internal structure of the CPSF specimens with a diameter of 3 mm and length of 3 mm. The specimen was mounted into a special compression rig and compressed step by step. After each step of compression, the specimen together with the loading device was scanned by Yxlon computed tomography system at 60 kV voltage and 37 μ A current, and then reconstructed by the Volume Graphics Studio max 2.1 with an approximate voxel size of 4 μ m. In order to minimize the loading device hiding the X-ray beam during the scans, a polycarbonate tube was used to transmit the load between the mobile grip and the fixed grip in the rig. In addition, the two cylindrical plates used to compress the specimen in the load rig were also made of polycarbonate. This technique enabled the in-situ compression tests with XMT observations. In this study the deformation steps were controlled at strain values of 0, 15%, 30%, 45% and 60%.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Quasi-static compressive behavior

Fig.1 shows a typical quasi-static compressive stress-strain curve of the developed CPSF. As previously reported about syntactic foams [11, 12], three different regions can be identified from the curve. The first region (I) is characterized by an almost linear portion in which the specimen deforms elastically. Then a peak stress, the compressive yield strength, is observed, which is the transition point between regions (I) and (II). Region (II) begins with a ~30% drop in stress, and then extend to a low slope plateau regime until the densification strain ϵ_D is reached. ϵ_D is one of the key parameters for foam materials, a common used definition was proposed to determine the parameter by Paul [13], in this method the densification strain is determined as the intersection of tangents to the stress-strain curve for the plateau and densification regions. For the CPSF in this study, the densification strain ϵ_D is ~60% as shown in Fig.1. Beyond the densification strain ϵ_D , the stress-strain curve falls in densification region (III). In this region most cenospheres are crushed and compacted; the syntactic foam is compressed and thus densified into a bulk material. The bulk material has a much higher compressive resistance, therefore the rapid increase of stress can be found in the stress-strain curve.

Figure 1: A typical compressive stress–strain curve showing different stages of deformation: (I) linear elastic region; (II) plastic collapse region; (III) final densification region.

Figure 2: 3D image and the orthogonal XMT slices of a CPSF specimen.

3.2 XMT characterization of microstructural features

Fig.2 shows the 3D image and the orthogonal XMT slices of the foam. 3D median filtering was used to reduce image noise, and the clear images were presented. Examination of the XMT volume revealed the size of the cenospheres was not a constant, but the distribution of the hollow spheres in the foam was random and uniform, resulting in a homogeneous microstructure in the foam. The three phases can be easily identified from the slices. The white rings were the cenospheres shell, inside which was the air with the highest grey level. The cenospheres were surrounded by the epoxy matrix, and its grey level was between the air and the cenosphere.

3.3 The damage evolution and associated mechanisms of the CPSF under compressive load

Fig.3 shows the reconstructed 2D slices (XZ plane) of the vertical central plane of the specimen at different deformation stages. The loading direction is along the vertical Z axis. The schematic of the corresponding damage is shown in Fig. 4.

Figure 3: The reconstructed 2D slices (XZ plane) of the vertical central plane of the specimen at different deformation stages.

From the observation of the first two XMT slices, it is found that the initial deformation of the cenospheres occurred in the central part of the specimen. It can be seen that the cenospheres were compressed into oblate spheroids. This is because the maximum hydrostatic stress occurs in the central part when a small compressive strain is applied, the detailed finite element analysis of the bulk syntactic foam model was reported by Li [14]. In addition, it is also found that the failure initiated at the larger cenospheres, while the small ones are almost intact. In the previous study the localized stress distribution within the syntactic foam was discussed [15]. The failure of the micro balloons is most likely to originate at the largest ones. The experiment results verify the previous modelling result.

With the increase of the strain, the barrelling effect raised the shear stress along the specimen diagonal [14]. Therefore the damage of the cenospheres extends to the shear band of the specimen at a nearly 45° angle to the loading axis (see the XMT slice at $\epsilon = 30\%$ in Fig.3). On the other hand, the oblate cenospheres in the central part were almost fully crushed, hence the adjacent cenospheres carried higher load, causing them to be crushed subsequently. In this process, the stress concentration preferentially transferred to the lateral sides of the first breakage cenospheres rather than the top or

bottom side because of the loading direction. At this deformation stage, there are 2 zones that still contain some spherical cenospheres (zone 1, 2 in the schematic, Fig.4) and another 2 zones in which most cenospheres are intact (zone 3, 4 in the schematic).

With the further increased strain, the hydrostatic stress and shear stress gradually make zone 1 and 2 the fully crushed area (Fig.4). At the same time, the damage area also extended vertically. This is because as the central part has been compressed compactly, there is no more space to be consumed by the matrix and the fragments of the broken cenospheres. Finally a damage band transversely across the specimen was formed as shown in the XMT slice of 45% strain (Fig.3) and the corresponding schematic (Fig.4). During this process, the damage area enlarged, and more and more cenospheres were involved in the damage evolution, therefore a higher load is required to continually compress the specimen. Hence the stress level gradually increases from 30% strain to 45% strain. Up to now, the damage of the specimen is dominated by the collapse of the cenospheres, while the matrix mainly deformed plastically. Though it is believed the localized fracture of the matrix has already occurred somewhere in the specimen, it may not affect the bulk mechanical behaviour of the specimen.

When the strain increased to 60%, the collapse of the cenospheres doesn't show much difference from that at the 45% strain slice (Fig.3). Though the zone 3 and 4 further shrink, there are still some spherical cenospheres unchanged (Fig.4). However, one more major feature of the failure can be observed, that is the large scale matrix crack as red marked in the XMT slice. The cracks were most likely caused by the shear stress, and propagated at a nearly 60° angle from the corner.

Figure 4: The schematic of the damage evolution of the CPSF.

Usually the crack separation mode can be different depending on the nature of localised stresses [16]. To better illustrate the matrix cracks, two typical XY plane slices are presented in Fig. 5. From the figure, two types of matrix cracks can be identified. One is marked in red, which can also be observed in the XZ plane slice. As the shear stress is responsible for such cracks and the cracks are also along the stress direction, they can be classified as the mode II crack. The other type of cracks was marked with yellow color, which may be induced by the hoop stress surrounding the cylinder which was produced by the lateral expansion of the specimen. The hoop stress is in a tensile condition, and the cracks propagate along the radius direction in the XY plane and longitudinal direction of the specimen. Thus such cracks are classified the mode I cracks,

Figure 5: The two typical XY plane slices at the strain value of 60%, and the schematic of the crack separation modes.

The damage history of the developed CPSF can be summarized as follow: 1) at the early stage of deformation, the compressive damage caused by hydrostatic stresses occurred in the central part of the foam specimen. 2) As the deformation increased, the barreling effect in the cylindrical specimen raised the shear stress along the specimen diagonal, the damage of the cenospheres extended to the shear band of the specimen. 3) Then, the hydrostatic stress fully crushed the central part and resulted in the densification, after that a damage band transversely across the specimen was formed. 4) Finally, the shear stress induced the macro-cracks in the epoxy matrix along the diagonal direction, and the longitudinal cracks also occurred on the surface of the specimen due to the hoop stress caused by the lateral expansion of the specimen. The large scale cracks resulted in the final failure of the specimen.

Figure 6: The XY plane slices of a typical cenosphere at deformation stages.

3.4 The failure mode of the individual cenosphere

Fig. 6 shows the 2D XY plane slices of a typical cenosphere at different strains. After examination of the slices, the failure process of an individual cenosphere can be identified. When the strain increased to 15%, a micro crack can be found on the bigger cenosphere shell. As the slice is on the XY plane, it is deduced that the crack should be along the loading direction (Z axis) and vertical to the equator of the cenosphere. With the increase of deformation, more and more micro cracks were formed on the shell and separate the cenosphere into several fragments (see the slice $\epsilon = 30\%$). The fragments were attached on the adjacent pore of the matrix. The failure mode of the cenospheres can be summarized as the vertical splitting. Similar result was also reported by Chung [17]. The cenosphere was finally compressed compactly; the fragments from the top and bottom of the cenosphere may touch each other. Hence almost the whole fragments can be seen in the last XY plane slice.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The quasi-static compressive behaviour and the associated failure mechanisms of the CPSF specimen were studied by the compression test and the in-situ compression tests with XMT inspections. It is found that the compressive behaviour of the developed CPSF can also be identified as the elastic, plateau and densification regions. The failure of the material initiates at the beginning of the plateau region, the initial deformation of the cenospheres occurred in the central part of the specimen caused by hydrostatic stresses. As the deformation increases, the barrelling effect in the cylindrical specimen raises the shear stress along the specimen diagonal. Then the hydrostatic stress fully crushes the central part and results in the densification. Finally the shear stress induces the macro-cracks in the epoxy matrix along the diagonal direction, and the longitudinal cracks are found on the surface of the specimen due to the lateral expansion caused by the hoop stress. The large scale cracks result in the total failure of the specimen. It was also observed cracks occurred in the cenospheres along the compression direction and separated an individual cenosphere into fragments. The failure mode of the cenospheres can be summarised as the vertical splitting.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was financially supported by the Nanyang Technological University (NTU) Start-up Grant. RH acknowledges the NTU Research Student Scholarship.

REFERENCES

- [1] J. K. Cochran, "Ceramic hollow spheres and their applications," *Current Opinion in Solid State & Materials Science*, vol. 3, pp. 474-479, Oct 1998.
- [2] Q. Zhang, P. D. Lee, R. Singh, G. Wu, and T. C. Lindley, "Micro-CT characterization of structural features and deformation behavior of fly ash/aluminum syntactic foam," *Acta Materialia*, vol. 57, pp. 3003-3011, Jun 2009.
- [3] A. Das and B. K. Satapathy, "Structural, thermal, mechanical and dynamic mechanical properties of cenosphere filled polypropylene composites," *Materials & design*, vol. 32, pp. 1477-1484, Mar 2011.
- [4] J. Gu, G. Wu, and Q. Zhang, "Effect of porosity on the damping properties of modified epoxy composites filled with fly ash," *Scripta Materialia*, vol. 57, pp. 529-532, Sep 2007.
- [5] V. K. Srivastava and P. S. Shembekar, "TENSILE AND FRACTURE PROPERTIES OF EPOXY-RESIN FILLED WITH FLY-ASH PARTICLES," *Journal of Materials Science*, vol. 25, pp. 3513-3516, Aug 1990.
- [6] G. H. Wu, Z. Y. Dou, D. L. Sun, L. T. Jiang, B. S. Ding, and B. F. He, "Compression behaviors of cenosphere-pure aluminum syntactic foams," *Scripta Materialia*, vol. 56, pp. 221-224, Feb 2007.
- [7] E. M. Wouterson, F. Y. C. Boey, X. Hu, and S. C. Wong, "Specific properties and fracture toughness of syntactic foam: Effect of foam microstructures," *Composites Science and Technology*, vol. 65, pp. 1840-1850, Sep 2005.
- [8] J. Y. Buffiere, E. Maire, J. Adrien, J. P. Masse, and E. Boller, "In Situ Experiments with X ray Tomography: an Attractive Tool for Experimental Mechanics," *Experimental Mechanics*, vol. 50, pp. 289-305, Mar 2010.
- [9] H. A. Bale, A. Haboub, A. A. MacDowell, J. R. Nasiatka, D. Y. Parkinson, B. N. Cox, D. B. Marshall, and R. O. Ritchie, "Real-time quantitative imaging of failure events in materials under load at temperatures above 1,600 degrees C," *Nature Materials*, vol. 12, pp. 40-46, Jan 2013.

- [10] E. Maire, "X-Ray Tomography Applied to the Characterization of Highly Porous Materials," *Annual Review of Materials Research, Vol 42*, vol. 42, pp. 163-178, 2012 2012.
- [11] E. M. Wouterson, F. Y. C. Boey, X. Hu, and S.-C. Wong, "Specific properties and fracture toughness of syntactic foam: Effect of foam microstructures," *Composites Science and Technology*, vol. 65, pp. 1840-1850, 2005.
- [12] P. Bunn and J. Mottram, "Manufacture and compression properties of syntactic foams," *Composites*, vol. 24, pp. 565-571, 1993.
- [13] A. Paul and U. Ramamurty, "Strain rate sensitivity of a closed-cell aluminum foam," *Materials Science and Engineering a-Structural Materials Properties Microstructure and Processing*, vol. 281, pp. 1-7, Apr 15 2000.
- [14] P. Li, N. Petrinic, C. R. Siviour, R. Froud, and J. M. Reed, "Strain rate dependent compressive properties of glass microballoon epoxy syntactic foams," *Materials Science and Engineering: A*, vol. 515, pp. 19-25, 2009.
- [15] R. Huang and P. Li, "Elastic behaviour and failure mechanism in epoxy syntactic foams: The effect of glass microballoon volume fractions," *Composites Part B: Engineering*, vol. 78, pp. 401-408, 2015.
- [16] P. Li, "Constitutive and failure behaviour in selective laser melted stainless steel for microlattice structures," *Materials Science and Engineering: A*, vol. 622, pp. 114-120, 2015.
- [17] J. H. Chung, J. K. Cochran, and K. J. Lee, "Compressive mechanical behavior of hollow ceramic spheres," in *Hollow and Solid Spheres and Microspheres: Science and Technology Associated with Their Fabrication and Application*. vol. 372, D. L. Wilcox, M. Berg, T. Bernat, D. Kellerman, and J. K. Cochran, Eds., ed, 1995, pp. 179-186.